

HadISDH.marine Update Document

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General Notes:

The HadISDH.marine.1.0.0.2019f contains all 12 months of 2019. There are no historical changes, bug fixes or minor or major code changes and so the X.Y.Z. version number remains the same. Keep up to date with subsequent changes and analyses at <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com>.

Version Number X.Y.Z.0000p/f:

1.0.0.2019f

Major Changes X:

- None

Minor Changes Y:

- None

Bug fixes / historical data updates Z:

- None

Start Date DD.MM.YYYY: 1973-01-01

End Date DD.MM.YYYY: 2019-12-31

Hadisdh Data Format (Baseline documentation): URL: <http://cedadocs.ceda.ac.uk/1477>

Reference: No change

Other notes: The HadISDH update/analyses blog is here: <https://hadisdh.blogspot.com>